

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE IDENTIFICATION LEVEL AND THE ORGANIZATIONAL CREATIVITY PERCEPTION LEVEL - SPORT İSTANBUL SAMPLE

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to analyze the relationship of the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level of the personnel of Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality Istanbul Sports Events and Trade Management Incorporated Company (Sport Istanbul). In line with the aim of the study, the personnel of Sport Istanbul has constituted the population of the study, and volunteer participants determined by simple random sampling method (n=285) have constituted the sample of the same. Survey method has been applied as the data collection tool. The participants have been applied a personal information form; the organizational identification scale developed by Ashforth (1992), Turkish transcription and validity and reliability study of which have been carried out by Polat (2009) and the organizational creativity scale developed by Balay (2010). Data obtained have been recorded by the package software "IBM SPSS 22". Spearman Correlation and Regression Analysis has been applied as the statistical process. In conclusion, it has been found that the organizational identification and organizational creativity perceptions of the personnel of Sport Istanbul are at a good level, there is a moderate positive relationship between the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level, and that the organizational identification affects the organizational creativity perception level positively. It may be thought that such situation results from personnel selection methods of the institution; adoption of the organizational vision and mission by the personnel; selection of personnel suitable for related job descriptions; utilization of the

personnel's capability, thoughts and characteristics, and the personnel's being in touch with managers in production of sport service.

Keywords: Sport Istanbul, organizational identification, organizational creativity

1. Introduction

Organizations making programs aimed at meeting the sport needs of people have their specific structures. There is no doubt that these organizations operate in the light of the general business enterprise principles like other service-producing enterprises do. However; the managers, officers, technical and assisted service elements who do their duty; prepare and present the sport services needed by people by using the field-specific information since each sport program includes a specialized knowledge. The common ground here is to provide and maintain the quality of the service. Service quality must be searched in the human factor on the focus of the relations between service providers and service consumers, i.e. the human factor. Therefore; efficiency and productivity of the enterprise in provision and preparation of the sport and service programs is -almost completely- up to the personnel. In this case, the precious and absolutely important source in sport management is human who provides service (Imamoğlu and Ekenci, 2014).

When Fayol (1917) opinion on enterprises "*effort must be made on various personnel staffs in order to provide high moral and goal congruence*". is considered together with Taylor (1911) opinion "*establishment of a sincere cooperation between managers and personnel*", regarded by him to be amongst the scientific management principles, it is emphasized that the personnel would achieve the organizational success with such senses as believing in organizational objectives, and loyalty.

It can be mentioned that there is an identification based on the psychological contract between the personnel who are in a continuous interaction with customers, and the organization in exhibition of their attitudes, information and skills.

Organizational identification can be defined as "*perception of belonging to an organization, and collaboration in case of success or failure of the organization*" (Ashforth and Mael, 1989);

"It has been found in the literature that the conclusions such as such factors as the level of the employees' interaction with their organizations, their existence in the organizations pulling them instead of the organizations pushing them, being a member of an organization meeting their personal objectives, and being working in a high-reputable organization would create more identification tendency in comparison to a low-reputable organization; and existence of large number of high-status works and individuals in the organization in which the employees work reinforces such identification tendency"

(Korkut, 1988; Nartgün and Kalay, 2014; fwd. Ocak et al. 2017)

It can be said that one of the basic grounds is "*the employees who feel not alienated in their organization and are provided to identify with their organization by diversity management*" (Gökçen and Çavuş, 2014). As well as the identification of the employee with the organization, the employee's suggestion of innovative and creative opinions also contributes to organizational success. Creativity is defined as "*A person's capability of producing new solutions and new results, thinking on something original that did not exist before, or setting forth new and different opinions*" (Gümüşsuyu, 2004). Organizational creativity has taken part in the literature as "*a valuable, useful and new service, opinion or process generated by the individuals who work together*" (Woodman et al. 1993).

Enterprises' achievement in their goals is up to "*their innovation-making capability in structural, technological and social issues by their creative intelligence and elasticity*" (Düren, 2000). Aim of this study is to analyze the relation between the organizational identification level and organizational creativity perception level of the personnel of Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality Istanbul Sports Events and Trade Management Incorporated Company (Sport Istanbul). It has been considered that handling the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level in the service sector, especially in the sport service sector where employees are considered significant, and determination of any effect of the employees' organizational identification level on the organizational creativity perception will contribute to the literature.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Formation of the Volunteer Groups

The personnel of Sport Istanbul has constituted the population of the study, and volunteer participants determined by simple random sampling method (n=285) have constituted the sample of the same. Volunteers have been requested to complete a socio-economic information form, and apply organizational identification and organizational creativity scales.

2.2 Socio-Demographic Information Form

Volunteers participating in the study have been asked for completing a personal information form consisting of 5 questions including in gender, marital status, age, professional experience, and level of income.

2.3 Organizational Identification Scale

In order to determine the organizational identification levels of the personnel working in sport services, the organizational identification scale, Mael and Ashforth (1992), developed by Mael and Ashforth (1992), Turkish transcription and validity and reliability study of which were carried out by Polat (2009) has been used. As a result of the reliability analysis, Mael and Ashforth (1992), the developers of the scale, has defined the reliability of the scale as 0.87. The scale has consisted of a single dimension and it cannot be separated into other dimensions. It has contained 6 items designed to

measure the identification senses of the employees. The scale items have been sorted in a 5-Point Likert-Type Scale rating form, namely "1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Unsure, 4-Agree, and 5-Strongly agree" (Polat, 2009).

2.4 Organizational Creativity Scale

The organizational creativity scale developed by Balay (2010) has been used in order to determine the organizational creativity perception levels of the individuals who work in sport services. Organizational creativity scale has consisted of 39 questions and three sub-dimensions. These sub-dimensions are; Individual (Items 1-16), Administrative (Articles 17-27) and Social (Articles 28 and 39) sub-dimensions. As a result of the reliability analysis, the coefficient of alpha internal consistency of the individual sub-division has been found as 92, that of the administrative sub-division found as 93, and of the social sub-division as 95. The scale has consisted of a rating form of 5-Point Likert-Type Scale including the items 1-Not at All, 2-Little, 3-Moderate, 4-A Lot, and 5-Full. According to such rating, the lowest score to get from the scale is 39, while the highest one is 195 (Balay, 2010).

2.5 Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from the personal information form and the personality scale has been statistically analyzed by the packaged software IBM SPSS 20.0. Personal information, inventory total scores and factor scores about the candidates have been given by determination of the frequency (f) and percentage (%) values. Spearman Correlation and Regression Analysis has been applied as the statistical procedure.

Table 1: Demographic Properties of the Participants

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	
Gender	Female	91	31.9
	Male	194	68.1
	Total	285	100
Marital Status	Single	102	35.8
	Married	183	64.2
	Total	285	100.0
Age	22-26 years	45	15.8
	27-31 years	92	32.3
	32-36 years	75	26.3
	37 years or over	73	25.6
	Total	285	100.0
Professional Experience	1-5 years	122	42.8
	6-10 years	73	25.6
	11 years or over	90	31.6
	Total	285	100.0
Level of Income	TRY 1800-2500	44	15.4
	TRY 2501-3200	128	44.9
	TRY 3201-3900	82	28.8
	TRY 3901 or over	31	10.9
	Total	285	100.0

When Table 1 is analyzed; it is seen that 31% of the participants are female, 68.1% of the same are male; 35.8% of them are single, 64.2% are married; 15.8% are at the ages between 22-26, 32.3% are between 27-31, 26.3% between 32-36, and 25.6% are at or over 37; 42.8% of them have professional experience of 1-5 years, 25.6% have that of 6-10 years, and 31.6% that of 11 years or over; 15.4% have the income level between TRY 1,800-2,500, 44.9% have that between TRY 2,501-3,200, 28.8% between TRY 3,201-3,900, and 10.9% of them have the income level of or over TRY 3,901.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Answers Given to the Scales by the Participants

	N	Min	Max	X±Sd
Organizational Identification	285	1.00	5.00	3.96±0.85
Organizational Creativity	285	1.03	5.00	3.66±0.58

In consideration of the analysis of Table 2, it has been found that the average score of organizational identification scale is 3.96±0.85, and the average score of organizational creativity scale is 3.66±0.58.

Table 3: Relationship between the Organizational Creativity Perception Level and Organizational Identification Level of the Participants

		1	2
Organizational Identification Level	r	1	
	p	-	
	n	285	
Organizational Creativity Level	r	0.543**	1
	p	0.000	-
	n	285	

As a result of the analysis of Table 3 it has been found that there is a moderate positive relationship ($r=0.543$, $p=0.000$) between the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level.

Table 4: Regression Analysis for Prediction of the Organizational Creativity Perception Level

	β	t	P	R	R ²	F	p
Constant				0.542	0.029	37.699	0.000
Organizational Identification Level	0.542	6.138	0.000				

When Table 4 is analyzed, it is found that there exists a significant relationship between the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level. ($R=0.542$, $R^2=0.029$; $p<0.001$). In consideration of the result of the t-test for significance of the regression coefficient, it is seen that the organizational identification level ($t=6.138$, $p=0.000$) predicts the organizational creativity perception level and demonstrates approximately 29% of the total variance.

4. Conclusion

It has been found that the average score of organizational identification scale is 3.96 ± 0.85 , and the average score of organizational creativity scale is 3.66 ± 0.58 . When the literature was searched, no study on employees of sport organization was found. When the studies made with various participant groups are analyzed, i.e. made by Yıldız (2013); it was seen that the average value of the identification level of the primary school teachers is $x=3.29$ ($S=0.71$) "unsure". Çakınberk et al. (2011) has found the identification level of the teachers high. It can be stated that high level of identification with organization can provide desired organizational outputs such as intra-organizational cooperation and organizational citizenship (Dutton et al. 1994). It has been found that the employees of Sport İstanbul replied all the questions constituting the sub-dimensions of the organizational creativity scale "strongly agree" (3.40-4.19), and that the organizational creativity level of the participants was high. When the literature is searched, it was determined by the study applied by Çimen et al. (2017) to the sport managers that the participants' individual dimension average of the organizational creativity scale was 4.01 ± 0.49 , administrative dimension average was 3.76 ± 0.69 , social dimension average was 3.58 ± 0.76 , and organizational creativity average was 3.81 ± 0.53 . Çimen et al. (2017) has stated that the organizational creativity perceptions of the sport managers were at a good level. This study has parallels with our findings. According to Yurter (2016), the organizational creativity behaviors of the teachers who participated in the study are at a high level. In the study, individual dimension average of the organizational creativity scale has been determined as 3.70 ± 0.50 , administrative dimension average as 3.18 ± 0.80 , and social dimension average as 3.34 ± 0.65 . According to Yurter (2016), the organizational creativity behaviors of the teachers who participated in the study are at a high level. The study made by Balay (2010) has set forth that the academicians perceive the individual dimension, one of the dimensions of the organizational creativity, at a "sufficient" level; and the administrative and social dimensions at a "moderate" level.

It has been found that there is a moderate positive relationship between the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level ($r=0.543$, $p=0.000$). Accordingly, it can be said that the organizational creativity perception level increases as long as the organizational identification level increases. It is thought that the sport enterprises need to develop their employees' perception of unity and solidarity with or that of belonging to the organization in order to develop the organizational creativity level. Likewise, it can be thought that it is important for organizations to help their personnel to know and adopt them and to review, update, and develop the processes by using different and innovative ideas of their personnel in order to achieve their target objectives. When the literature is searched, no study on relationship between the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level was found. Other various studies on the organizational creativity and the organizational identification show that the organizational identification correlates with the organizational support perceptions. Barutcu (2015)

affirmed that “*there is a linear relationship between the organizational climate and the organizational creativity*”. Yahşı (2014) confirms, “*there exists positive relationships between leadership behaviors, organizational creativity, and personnel performance*”. Yılmaz and Karahan (2010) Organizational creativity and organizational identification are important for organizations. Because, adoption of the organization by the personnel has importance in terms of cooperation, communication, “*creative behavior, increasing social support, helping behavior in work stress times, and positive evaluation of the organization*” (Ashforth et al. 2008), and adaptation of the organizational innovative ideas to advancing technology.

It has been seen that there exists a significant relationship between the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level. It can be found by analysis of the t-test results for significance of the regression coefficient that the organizational identification level predicts the organizational creativity perception level, and demonstrates approximately 29% of the total variance.

Another study has set forth that the process and interpersonal justice dimensions affect the organizational identification positively, and that employees' level of identification with their organizations increases as long as their process and interpersonal justice perceptions increase (Cüce et al. 2013). When the literature is analyzed, it would be seen that no study researching on the effects of the organizational identification on the organizational creativity perception level. If the other studies in the literature are reviewed; it would be found that the organizational identification affects the organizational citizenship behavior positively Karabey and İřcan (2007), Yılmaz and Karahan (2010) have determined that the vision-focused leadership behavior, one of the dimensions concerning the leadership behavior, affects the organizational creativity.

In conclusion, it has been found that the organizational identification and the organizational creativity perceptions of the personnel of Sport Istanbul are at a good level; there exists a moderate positive relationship between the organizational identification level and the organizational creativity perception level; and that the organizational identification affects the organizational creativity perception level positively.

It can be thought that such situation results from the institute's personnel selection techniques, making the personnel adopt the organization's vision and mission; selection of the personnel qualified for the jobs described; taking the advantages of ability, opinion and property of the personnel; and being in contact with the managers in production of sport services.

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